

2022 ANNUAL REPORT

RESEARCH AT THE HEART OF EUROPE'S AMBITION

**SCIENCE
EUROPE**
Shaping the future of research

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FOREWORD

“Science Europe engaged in several activities in 2022 that have resulted in important advancements that I believe will shape our research system for years to come.”

As we reflect on the events that shaped 2022, it is impossible not to start with the outbreak of the war in Ukraine. Science Europe and its members condemned the military aggression and swiftly committed to providing support to Ukrainian researchers in various ways. They also welcomed the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU) as a member. The tragic events in Ukraine have once again highlighted the resilience of the research ecosystem and the crucial importance of global collaboration, especially in times of crisis.

For Science Europe, 2022 was the first full year of implementing the Strategy Plan 2021–2026. A renewed Governing Board kicked off the year and the new Working Groups set themselves ambitious work programmes. Their work and expertise are instrumental in pursuing our mission of defining long-term perspectives for European research and championing best-practice approaches, while ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of society.

This Annual Report highlights the most significant contributions from 2022 to our priority areas. Science Europe engaged in

meaningful dialogue with key stakeholders at the EU and international level, consolidating our position as a trusted partner in shaping research policies and ensuring that our members' input is integrated into Horizon Europe. We put a spotlight on brain circulation, developing comprehensive recommendations to reduce disparity in R&I and promote wider participation and excellence. Last but not least, we have initiated an important dialogue on ethics and integrity in the context of public engagement of research in society.

Science Europe contributed to driving broader cultural transformation within the European research landscape and on a global scale. Our values framework set the foundation for a common reference towards healthier and more effective research culture. Our conference on Open Science and the accompanying direction paper reflected a dynamic acceleration in the transition to Open Science. In parallel, we worked with our partners to bring together a community in support of the Diamond Open Access publishing model. The momentum behind our efforts to promote the reform of evaluation processes continued to grow with the establishment of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

We also shed light on the role of science in addressing societal challenges by analysing interdisciplinary research for the green and digital transition. Additionally, we launched a visionary plan for science communication, emphasising our collective efforts to effectively communicate research outcomes and their societal impact.

In developing our activities, we also joined forces with R&I partners such as the OECD-Global Science Forum, university associations, and the Global Research Council. Our achievements would not be possible without mutual collaboration with our partners in the wider research community and stakeholder groups.

I would like to thank all Science Europe members for their expertise and continued engagement, my colleagues on the Governing Board for their valuable strategic input and guidance, and the staff in the Office for their work and dedication to the organisation.

Together, we can build a stronger research landscape that fosters collaboration, innovation, and equity.

MARC SCHILTZ
PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE

2022 OUTPUTS AT A GLANCE

Q1

JANUARY

- Almost all Science Europe Working Groups have elected their Chair(s)
- 2nd High-Level Exchange with the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)
- [Joined the Forum of Universities for the Future of Europe](#)
- Ideas launched for the [Future of Europe conference](#)

FEBRUARY

- [Statement of Support to Ukraine](#)
- Workshop on [Diamond Open Access](#) (online) with the support of the French Presidency of the Council of the EU
- [Science in the 21st century? Not without girls and women!](#) campaign
- Contribution to the ERA Forum R&I Stakeholder Meetings
- Supported the [Stick to Science](#) movement, to speed up the association agreements with Switzerland and the UK
- [First informal assessment of Horizon Europe](#)

MARCH

- [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#) published
- Promotion of Members' Activities in Support of Ukraine
- [Science for Net-Zero Transition Symposium](#) report published
- Joined the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) 20th Anniversary Conference
- 1st stakeholder assembly on the European Reform of Research Assessment Initiative

Q2

APRIL

- First [Diamond Open Access Community Webinar](#)
- [Good Advice for \(Young\) Science Policy Advisors](#), Side event to SAPEA Conference
- [‘Science Under Pressure’](#)

MAY

- 2nd Stakeholder Assembly on the European Reform of Research Assessment Initiative
- [Science Europe Membership Expands to Forty](#)
- 1st Members Workshop on Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation in European Programmes

JUNE

- Attended the Global Research Council Annual Meeting (Panama City)
- Reaction to Council [Conclusions on Research Assessment and Open Science](#) Position Statement
- [A Values Framework for the Organisation of Research](#)
- Position Statement on [Science Communication for Greater Research Impact](#)

Q3

JULY

- Science Europe [2021 Annual Report](#)
- Contributed to [EuroScience Open Forum 2022](#) (Leiden, the Netherlands)
- [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) final and public
- Expression of commitments to ERA Policy Agenda 2022–2024
- Second [Diamond Open Access Community Webinar](#)
- [Science Europe Public Newsletter](#)

SEPTEMBER

- 2nd Members Workshop on Spreading Excellence and Widening Participation in European Programmes
- [Diamond Open Access Conference](#) (Zadar, Croatia)
- [Launch of the Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA)

Q4

OCTOBER

- [Joined Science and Technology in Society Forum](#) (STS forum, Kyoto, Japan)
- Science Europe [Open Science Conference](#) (online, Brussels)
- [Direction Paper on Open Science as Part of a Well-Functioning Research System](#)
- [Joined 10th meeting of the ERA Forum](#)

NOVEMBER

- [Interdisciplinarity for The Net-Zero Transition](#) (Online COP27 Lead-up Event)
- [Interdisciplinary Research for the Green and Digital Transition Report](#)
- [Talent Retention: How can Europe tackle the challenges of Brain Drain and Capacity Building in EU-13 countries?](#) Conference (Prague, Czech Republic)
- Position Statement [Towards Strengthened Research and Innovation Systems across Europe](#)
- ‘Facing global challenges during a Paradigm Shift of Science’ workshop by Science Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC)
- First Workshop on Global Equity in Open Access Publishing
- [High Level Workshop on ERA on Research Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Public Engagement](#) (Zurich, Switzerland)
- [#TalkingScience with High Integrity and Ethics Standards Campaign](#)

DECEMBER

- Briefing Paper on EOSC: [Federating Research Infrastructures in Europe for Fair Access to Data](#)
- [Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) Steering Board elected
- [Joined the 10th World Science Forum \(WSF\)](#) (Cape Town, South Africa)
- [Global Research Council European Regional Meeting](#) (UK)
- [High-level Exchange with the National Natural Science Foundation of China \(NSFC\) Governing Board](#)

TOP ACHIEVEMENTS

The publication of the **Values Framework for the Organisation of Research** as a foundation for future discussions on research culture, thanks to the efforts of the Working Group on Research Culture.

The work on open science which included the **Open Science Conference** and the publication of a **Direction Paper**, both achieved through the efforts of the Working Group on Open Science. Special emphasis was placed on the launch of the **Action Plan for Diamond Open Access** and bringing together a community in support of this publishing model.

The publication of a set of **Recommendations to Reduce Research and Innovation Disparities and Foster Brain Circulation**, resulting from the joint work of the Task Force on Widening Activities, part of the Working Group on Horizon Europe.

The publication of the **Report on Interdisciplinary Research for the Green and Digital Transition**, which traces the contribution of the Working Group on the Green and Digital Transition.

The organisation of the High Level Workshop on the ERA, addressing **Research Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Public Engagement**.

The publication of a **Position Statement on Science Communication** to improve the impact and dissemination of research, drafted by the Working Group on Communication.

The launch of the **Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment** and the **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)**, where Science Europe worked closely with the European University Association and the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation of the European Commission.

MAP OF SCIENCE EUROPE MEMBERS

1 FWF Der Wissenschaftsfonds.	2 ÖAW ÖSTERREICHISCHE AKADEMIE DER WISSENSCHAFTEN	3 fns LA LIBERTÉ DE CHERCHER	4 fwo Research Foundation Flanders Opening new horizons
5	6 HRZZ Croatian Science Foundation	7 GAČR CZECH SCIENCE FOUNDATION	8
9	10	11	12 anr agence nationale de la recherche
13 DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft German Research Foundation	14	15	16
17 HRB Health Research Board	18	19	20
21	22	23	24
25	26	27	28
29	30	31	32
33	34	35	36 FORTE Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare
37 FORMAS	38	39	40
41			

2022 IN NUMBERS

GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS 2022

The Science Europe Governing Board is the senior body of elected members which is entrusted by the General Assembly to define, guide, and monitor the strategic direction of the association. It consists of at least nine Heads of Science Europe's Member Organisations, including a President and two Vice-Presidents. Governing Board members are elected by the General Assembly for a term of two years.

Marc Schiltz
President
Secretary General
of the Luxembourg
National Research
Fund (FNR)
Luxembourg

Ángeles Gómez Borrego
Vice-President
representing RPOs*
Vice-President for
International Affairs
of the Spanish
National Research
Council (CSIC)
Spain

*(Until July)

Angelika Kalt
Vice-President
representing RFOs
Director of the
Swiss National
Science Foundation
(SNSF)
Switzerland

Adrian Curaj
Director General
of the Executive
Agency for
Higher Education,
Research,
Development
and Innovation
Funding of
Romania
(UEFISCDI)
Romania

Thierry Damerval
President/CEO
of the French
National Research
Agency (ANR)
France

Matthias Koenig
Vice-President
of the German
Research
Foundation (DFG)
Germany

Marcel Levi
President of the
Dutch Research
Council (NWO)
Netherlands

Mari Sundli Tveit
Chief Executive
of the Research
Council of Norway
(RCN)
Norway

Melanie Welham
Executive Chair
of the UK Research
and Innovation
(UKRI)
United Kingdom

Antonio Zoccoli
President of the
National Institute
for Nuclear Physics
(INFN)
Italy

VISION AND MISSION

Science Europe is the association representing major public organisations that fund or perform excellent, ground-breaking scientific research in Europe. It brings together the expertise of some of the largest and best-known research organisations in the world to jointly push the frontiers of how scientific research is produced and delivers benefits to society.

VISION

Science Europe's vision is for a European Research Area with optimal conditions to support robust education, research, and innovation systems. This is a European Research Area where science is a strong and trusted component of sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

MISSION

Science Europe's mission is to define long-term perspectives for European research and to champion best-practice approaches, ensuring high-quality science for the benefit of humanity and the planet.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021 - 2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021 - 2026](#)

STRATEGY PLAN

The Strategy Plan has three strategic priorities that encapsulate Science Europe’s vision:

- Shape European research policy developments
- Contribute to the evolution of research culture
- Strengthen the role and contribution of science in tackling societal challenges

SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN PRIORITIES AND TOPICS

Every strategic priority encompasses various specific topics. Correlations can be identified within the strategic areas and across the various topics.

REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

[Science Europe Strategy Plan 2021 - 2026](#)

[Multi-Annual Action Plan 2021 - 2026](#)

SUPPORTING UKRAINE

The ongoing Russian war of aggression against Ukraine is causing many casualties, displacing millions of people, and destroying a large amount of infrastructures. Science Europe and its members strongly **support the Ukrainian research ecosystem** and its member in the country, the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU).

The Russian invasion has had alarming effects on the education and research system of Ukraine. According to data from the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine and the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, more than 130 universities and colleges are damaged, and over 50 research institutions have been damaged or destroyed.

Science Europe and its Member Organisations condemned the Russian hostilities and set up numerous initiatives to support the people of Ukraine, including its researchers and research ecosystem. These range from hosting researchers and providing shelter for refugees to using existing and new funding mechanisms to fund Ukrainian researchers, as well as developing joint calls with Ukrainian institutions. The association has curated a [webpage](#) to make information easily accessible and available to all interested parties.

Science Europe welcomed the NRFU to its membership in 2022, which has been actively contributing to its activities since. The association has repeatedly called for a cessation of hostilities and respect for international law and human rights. It has continuously advocated the European and international research community to keep working together to take all possible actions in support of Ukrainian researchers.

“The Ukrainian research community is at the forefront of world-leading research in many scientific fields. With NRFU as a valued member since 2022, we express unwavering solidarity with the people of Ukraine. Our members remain steadfast in their support for the Ukrainian research community, fostering deeper collaborations with key stakeholders.”

LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN / SECRETARY GENERAL OF SCIENCE EUROPE

Executive Director of the National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU) **Olga Polotska** at the Science Europe High-Level Workshop on the European Research Area, Zurich, Switzerland, November 2022

www.scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/ukraine/

Statement of Support for Ukraine and Ukrainian Science Day

<http://scieur.org/supportukraine>

ACTIVITY AREAS

CONTRIBUTE TO THE EVOLUTION OF RESEARCH CULTURE

PERFORMANCE
KEVIN MURPHY
&
MATHIEU LEBRAUN

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

RESEARCH CULTURE

Contributing to policies and practices that empower researchers through a prospering research system is at the heart of our priorities. This includes improving career systems to attract the most talented and innovative researchers and maintaining excellence in all research assessment processes and practices.

Science Europe and its Member Organisations collectively aspire to foster positive culture shifts to create attractive and sustainable research ecosystems where researchers can thrive. To achieve this, the association published a shared [Values Framework](#) in June 2022. The framework highlights six central values and provides a foundation for appraisal and adaptation, with a clear ambition to steer the evolution of research culture. The Working Group on Research Culture continues to discuss how to embed these values in institutional policies and practices.

“Research culture touches upon the core business of research organisations. We are at a turning point in our reflection on how policies and practices influence all aspects of the research ecosystem and on how to empower researchers in their endeavours.”

MARC SCHILTZ / PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE AND SECRETARY GENERAL OF THE LUXEMBOURG NATIONAL RESEARCH FUND

Drawing from Science Europe's 2021 [Statement on Research Culture](#), the framework allows for a flexible approach, while acknowledging the fundamental values underlying research processes and outcomes, together with research management and governance. It intends to provide a basis for recommendations on research assessment criteria within a project on recognition systems, and discussions in the framework of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#) (CoARA).

RECOGNISING WHAT WE VALUE

Science Europe committed to transforming recognition systems to foster healthy research cultures. To achieve this, the association initiated a two-year project that aimed to facilitate mutual learning and knowledge sharing among its members.

The project 'Recognising What We Value' is a continuation of the activities focused on research assessment processes carried out in 2020. Based on the Values Framework, this project will provide a set of overarching recommendations for assessment criteria that, once published, will feed into the work of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment.

RESEARCH CAREERS

As part of its pledge to enhance the appeal of research-related careers, Science Europe followed through on its commitment from the same 2021 [Statement on Research Culture](#). The aim is to improve the stability and sustainability of European research by recognising a broader range of roles, especially the contribution of early-career researchers in collaborative and team research, thereby increasing the attractiveness of careers for talented individuals.

The association organised a dedicated session during the [EuroScience Open Forum \(ESOF\)](#) in July, in Leiden, the Netherlands. The session mapped the key challenges researchers face when pursuing careers in research, and proved decisive in stressing how current reward and incentive structures reward what is best for individuals, rather than for research quality. The event further served to showcase commitment by participants to adopt processes more inclusive and supportive of diversity, with a specific focus on early-career researchers.

REFORM OF RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Shedding light on well-known limitations that plague research recognition systems, Science Europe calls for research assessment systems to stop focusing on journal-based indicators. Instead, it advocates value-centred recognition systems where qualitative research and positive research cultures are preserved.

In 2022, Science Europe made significant progress on its long-standing priority of the reform of research assessment. Together with the [European University Association \(EUA\)](#) and the [European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation \(DG RTD\)](#), the association built on work that started in 2018, culminating in the public launch of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) in July 2022.

This agreement was based upon the [scoping work](#) conducted in 2021. Progress kept coming apace in the following months, resulting in Science Europe co-hosting the Constitutive Assembly of the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) in December. Between the launch of signatures in September and the end of the year, over 420 organisations signed the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, with 80% of the association's total membership having joined.

CoARA represents a wide range of organisations involved in research assessment and their respective associations. Within the coalition, signatories of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment gather to ease the exchange of information and mutual learning to set a shared direction for changes in research assessment practices with the overarching goal to maximise the quality and impact of research.

“What we have achieved with the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment in such a short amount of time is incredible. So many organisations have joined the movement and aim to recognise the full breadth of value created by researchers.”

MARC SCHILTZ / PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE AND SECRETARY GENERAL OF THE LUXEMBOURG NATIONAL RESEARCH FUND

coara.eu

The vision of CoARA is that the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations recognises the diverse outputs, practices and activities that maximise the quality and impact of research. This requires basing assessment primarily on qualitative judgement, for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-assessment

EQUALITY, DIVERSITY, AND INCLUSION

Science Europe believes that all research environments should guarantee that scholars can reach their fullest potential, irrespective of their gender, sexual orientation, religion, disabilities, ethnic origin, or social background.

In 2022, a review of Science Europe's 2017 Practical Guide to Improving Gender Equality in Research Organisations started, with the goal to explore how diversity and intersectionality are interwoven within the research ecosystems. To better understand key challenges that research organisations face when supporting diversity, a survey for the Member Organisations was developed. Launched in early 2023, the survey will serve as a foundation for an updated practical guide, also foreseen in 2023.

At global level, the association shared insights and expertise from its Member Organisations on multiple occasions throughout the year, via the Global Research Council's (GRC) Working Group on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion. This included a side event during the GRC Annual Meeting in May, with a focus on how to address harassment and bullying in research, and a workshop on promoting equitable and fair research careers in November.

To follow up both lines of work, the GRC Working Group on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion and Science Europe planned to develop guidelines on harassment and bullying in research, as well as to conduct a series of workshops until the end of 2023. These workshops are expected to address relevant issues such as research careers, combatting bullying and harassment, and integrating the gender dimension in research.

"By addressing inequality and promoting inclusion and diversity, research organisations not only strengthen the scientific ecosystem, but also contribute to progress in wider society."

MELANIE WELHAM / EXECUTIVE CHAIR OF THE BIOTECHNOLOGY AND BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES RESEARCH COUNCIL, UK RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (UKRI)

RESEARCH INTEGRITY AND ETHICS

Research integrity and ethical behaviour precondition excellent science and scholarship. Science Europe calls for enhanced research integrity policies to pave the way for a well-functioning research environment in Europe, and beyond.

In 2022, following up a consultation run by ALLEA, Science Europe was invited to provide input to the update of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, which is the European reference for good research practice. Further discussions on a position on Research Integrity are expected to continue in 2023.

In the aftermath of the 2022 High-Level Workshop on research integrity and ethics in the context of public engagement, the dedicated task force was set to undertake parallel activities in 2023, addressing issues arising from the workshop outcomes, and the global charter on research ethics and integrity (see section on the European Research Area).

Similarly, the Science Europe campaign #TalkingScience with High Integrity and Ethics Standards showcased more than 30 initiatives from 14 Member Organisations and was launched at the High-Level Workshop on ERA in November. The initiatives included communicating with a broader audience, citizen science projects, and interaction with policy makers. They covered a wide range of issues: citizen science projects, a framework for science communication courses in higher education, patient and public involvement in clinical research proposals, national awards for science communication, guidance on citizen science, and much more. Work on research integrity and ethics will continue during 2023 and beyond.

“Research integrity and ethical behaviour lie at the heart of excellent science. They also play an important role in framing interactions between researchers and non-academics. Our responsibility is to further develop principles and guidelines for ethics in public engagement.”

ANGELIKA KALT / VICE PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE AND DIRECTOR OF THE SWISS NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION (SNSF)

scienceeurope.org/events/high-level-workshop-on-era-2022

OPEN SCIENCE

Science Europe and its Member Organisations are dedicated to promoting open science as an integral component of an effective research system. In 2022, this strategic objective was established at the core of its collective responsibility to shape the future of research within Europe and beyond.

The goal to turn open science into a practical reality was expanded in 2022. Science Europe established the objective to facilitate seamless collaboration between all participants involved in the research process while ensuring open access to research outcomes. Additionally, it endorsed the meaningful participation of societal actors in research activities when appropriate.

The basis for these objectives was set forth in a [Direction Paper on Open Science](#), unveiled in October 2022 at the [Science Europe Conference on Open Science](#), discussed across two days by 36 expert speakers and more than 600 participants, and developed in close collaboration with the Working Group on Open Science.

Together with various partners across Europe and beyond, the association also spearheaded efforts to bring together the research sector around a set of shared objectives. In March 2022, it was among the launch partners of the [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](#), which has been endorsed by numerous organisations and individuals worldwide. This plan outlines a series of critical steps to advance and promote a sustainable, community-driven Diamond scholarly communication ecosystem. The first [Diamond Open Access Conference](#), on 19–20 September in Zadar (Croatia), brought together the community of endorsers of the Action Plan and provided insights and inspiration to operationalise the plan. At the same time, the association started work as a task leader in the 2022–2025 Horizon Europe project [Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication \(DIAMAS\)](#). This growing community will meet for the second time in October 2023 during the [‘Global Summit on Diamond Open Access’](#).

Science Europe and its members are increasingly acknowledged as significant contributors to the EU’s policy conversations regarding open science. Leveraging its prior efforts in this domain and carving out a reputation for being a progressive advocate for open science, the organisation was frequently requested to participate and engage in policy initiatives aimed at promoting a scholarly communication ecosystem that is publicly owned and non-profit. Some instances of such initiatives included the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#), [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#), and deliberations on open science taking place within the European Research Area (ERA). The focus in 2023 will be to craft a shared vision of ORE as a pan-European publication platform.

“Open Science is not just a principle, it is a fundamental commitment to a well-functioning research system, where collaboration between all actors and open access to research outputs are fostered, and societal actors are meaningfully involved.”

THIERRY DAMERVAL /
PRESIDENT/CEO OF THE FRENCH NATIONAL
RESEARCH AGENCY (ANR)

<http://scieur.org/osconf-wrapup>

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/open-science

SHAPE EUROPEAN RESEARCH POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA

Science Europe continually pushes for the European Research Area (ERA) to act as the EU-wide space where high quality education, research, and innovation systems can thrive. The ERA is the place where science underlies sustainable economic, environmental, and societal development.

Throughout the year, Science Europe consistently advocated its members' views and priorities on the [ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024](#). This was achieved through regular contributions made during the monthly meetings of the ERA Forum, which allowed Science Europe to shape the ERA Actions in the Policy Agenda.

Science Europe continued its advocacy to open the ERA Forum to the research stakeholders and played a prominent role as the representative of its membership and other research performing organisations in Europe.

The association committed to ten ERA Actions, selected by consensus with its High-Level Policy Network. Contributions to these Actions focused on issues linked to data and digital legislation, as well as the development of the Framework on Research Careers. Additionally, the association leveraged its members' views on the

Science Diplomacy Agenda and the Team Europe approach to China, through the ERA subforum on the Global Approach to Research and Innovation.

HIGH-LEVEL WORKSHOP ON THE ERA

Science Europe held its fourteenth [High Level Workshop on the ERA](#), entitled 'Research Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Public Engagement', on 23 and 24 November. This major event, co-organised by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) and the Swiss State Secretariat for Education and Research and Innovation (SERI), explored the ways in which research, policy and the public interact. It also looked at possible avenues to generate better co-operation between policy makers, researchers, and a broader audience in terms of communication, expectation management, and training needs. One of the major outcomes of the workshop was a call for a global charter on research ethics and integrity and the commitment to involve citizens in research activities in a more systematic and efficient manner.

"The ERA is the cornerstone of scientific development in the EU. It promotes researcher mobility, incentivises R&I investments, improves diversity in science, and fosters collaboration between different stakeholders."

MARCEL LEVI / PRESIDENT OF THE DUTCH RESEARCH COUNCIL (NWO)

EU FRAMEWORK PROGRAMMES HORIZON EUROPE

Both Science Europe and its Member Organisations offer abundant knowledge and expertise for the European Union to tap into. This is particularly the case when it comes to guiding the EU on its flagship Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation, such as Horizon Europe.

Leveraging the potential of Europe's existing talent, developing new capacities, and optimising and spreading the benefits of research and innovation throughout the EU, are more important than ever before. Capitalising on the expertise of the association, a dedicated task force was set up under the Working Group on Horizon Europe with the aim to promote wider participation and excellence across the Member Organisations. This facilitated the exchange of information and enhanced the knowledge of national and EU funding instruments and resources among them. As part of its efforts to promote 'brain circulation' and counter the 'brain drain' phenomenon,

Science Europe organised three interactive workshops, two internal to gather Members' knowledge and experience and a public one.

The [public workshop](#) was co-organised with Science|Business on 9 and 10 November in Prague, as part of the events of the Czech Presidency of the EU Council. This public event served as a platform for the association to promote its [policy paper](#) entitled 'Recommendations to Reduce Research and Innovation Disparities and Foster Brain Circulation'. It advocates increased national investments in R&I, a stronger research culture, better talent retention, enhanced R&I capacity,

improved networking opportunities, and greater diversity in research culture.

In parallel, Science Europe kept its commitment to monitor institutional developments in the negotiations on the association of the United Kingdom and Switzerland. It provided support to the [Stick to Science](#) initiative that calls for scientific collaboration with the UK and Switzerland to take precedence over political considerations.

Together with its members, the association kickstarted the year by assessing the relevance and internal coherence of Horizon 2020 and its policy mix. In early 2023, it responded to the European Commission consultation on the performance of the European Research and Innovation Framework programmes 2014–2027. It offered the views of its members on both Horizon 2020 and the implementation of the first part of Horizon Europe. The main messages included concerns about insufficient budget, a call for a stronger role for social sciences and humanities, a more open and less competitive approach, and efficient co-ordination between national and European initiatives and policy developments.

“As the main EU funding instrument for R&I, the EU Framework Programme is a crucial tool for boosting excellent research and fostering collaboration at the European level.”

ADRIAN CURAJ / DIRECTOR GENERAL OF THE EXECUTIVE AGENCY FOR HIGHER EDUCATION, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATION FUNDING OF ROMANIA (UEFISCDI)

As part of its efforts to promote 'brain circulation' and counter the 'brain drain' phenomenon, Science Europe advocates:

- Increased national investments in R&I
- Stronger research culture
- Better talent retention
- Enhanced R&I capacity
- Improved networking opportunities
- Greater diversity in research culture

scieur.org/report-spreading-excellence

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-framework-programmes

EU LEGISLATION

It is in the DNA of Science Europe to put forward the voice and opinions of its members. Its influence on EU research-related legislation proposals is therefore paramount to protecting the membership's collective interests. In this regard, the association enjoys a long-standing status as the EU's trusted and reliable partner.

Science Europe continued to contribute to EU legislation developments, particularly in the area of research data. The Digital Services Act (DSA), which was under negotiation between the Council of the EU and the European Parliament, aimed to create a safer digital space where the fundamental rights of users are protected and to establish a level playing field for businesses. Nevertheless, the DSA was likely to generate legal uncertainty and fragmentation for the research sector and thus threatened some of the needs and specificities of the research and education sectors in policy and legislative developments in the digital field.

The association paired with the [European University Association \(EUA\)](#), [Sparc Europe](#), [COAR](#), and [LIBER](#), to jointly call for non-profit educational and scientific repositories, digital archives, and libraries to be exempted from the DSA. This joint call was particularly important since not-for-profit educational and scientific repositories were likely to fall in the scope of the DSA and thereby incur additional administrative and financial costs, despite the legislation being aimed at commercial platforms.

In the context of its sustained contribution to the ERA (see section on the [European Research Area](#)), Science Europe provided specific input to ERA Action 2 on how to make an EU copyright and data legislative and regulatory framework fit for research. This contribution was put forth during a European Commission workshop held on 23 June. A follow-up workshop was scheduled to take place in early 2023.

“To reinforce Europe’s world-class research, it is essential to have a regulatory framework in place that benefits research excellence, openness, and international collaboration.”

MATTHIAS KOENIG / VICE PRESIDENT OF THE GERMAN RESEARCH FOUNDATION (DFG)

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/eu-legislation

INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

As globalised research systems are becoming increasingly complex, optimal collaboration becomes a precondition for well-functioning research. Nowhere is international collaboration better illustrated than through the Global Research Council, where many Science Europe members take part in activities at regional and/or global levels.

Science Europe remains committed to promoting and facilitating more effective collaboration between research organisations at the international level through the efforts of its High-Level Policy Network.

CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

The association tackled several areas that lie at the heart of cross-border collaboration, including addressing foreign interference in research and innovation, and developing indicators to monitor the impact of cross-border collaboration.

To address concerns related to foreign interference, Member Organisations shared experiences and best practices, recognising that mutual learning is essential to tackling the challenges posed by collaboration with third countries. In this framework, the association addressed issues of reciprocity and academic freedom when partnering with third countries. These discussions have supported Members in developing concrete policy instruments to respond to the challenges caused by foreign interference.

In addition, the task force on Monitoring Cross-Border Collaboration (part of the High-Level Policy Network) completed the first phase of the project aimed at developing a common set of indicators to assess the impact of investments in cross-border collaboration. This first phase produced a 'Frame of Reference' which captured the perceived benefits and hoped-for impacts of cross-border collaboration.

COLLABORATION WITH THE NATIONAL NATURAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION OF CHINA

Science Europe and the National Natural Science Foundation of China (NSFC) have continued to explore ways to enhance their co-operation. A [joint policy workshop](#) held in November focused on 'the paradigm shift in science and its effect in addressing global challenges and achieving sustainable development'. The workshop highlighted the importance of interdisciplinary research for driving innovation and emphasised the global need to build bridges and promote co-operation, transparency, and data sharing as openly as possible.

GLOBAL RESEARCH COUNCIL

Science Europe played a significant role in the [Global Research Councils](#) (GRC) work, contributing to the development of a [statement of principles](#) covering research ethics, integrity and culture in the context of rapid results, and a [statement on workforce development in science and technology](#). This started through co-organising the European Regional Meeting of the GRC with the Spanish National Research Council in 2021. The statements were finally endorsed at the tenth GRC Annual Meeting from 30 May to 3 June in Panama, where the association co-chaired the European Regional Session, further cementing its pivotal role in GRC activities.

Science Europe and UK Research and Innovation co-organised the GRC European Regional Meeting in December 2022, which discussed the topics to be addressed at the GRC Annual Meeting in The Hague in 2023.

The Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway, Mari Sundli Tveit, was elected to the GRC Governing Board in May 2022, ensuring continued strong ties with the GRC.

“Knowledge production transcends national borders. Science Europe fully supports the development of mechanisms for cross-border collaboration and contribute to the development of international dialogue.”

ANGELIKA KALT /
VICE PRESIDENT OF SCIENCE EUROPE
AND DIRECTOR OF THE SWISS NATIONAL
SCIENCE FOUNDATION (SNSF)

Global Research Council European Regional Meeting (UK), December 2022

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/cross-border-collaboration

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES

Building robust research ecosystems relies heavily on investing in research infrastructures. Science Europe prioritises actions to support the financing, managing, and operating of national research infrastructures with a dual perspective of collaboration and international co-ordination.

In 2022, research infrastructures remained central to the ERA, with the association emphasising the importance of international collaboration in providing services, facilities, and resources. The organisation also engaged in activities where it highlighted how national public funding shaped both the European and the global infrastructure contexts.

Science Europe actively participated in the European Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Stakeholder Forum, in October in Brno (Czech Republic), promoting good practices and identifying bottlenecks that hinder a more efficient and responsive use of research infrastructure on an international scale.

Additionally, the association and its Member Organisations were consulted by the OECD-Global Science Forum on Very Large Research Infrastructures, further exemplifying their commitments to research infrastructures.

Science Europe followed up on its contribution during a side event at the International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI 2022), engaging in discussions on the development of a global ecosystem of research infrastructures. A report on Very Large Research Infrastructures is expected later this year.

“Research infrastructures are an important component in the realisation of the European Research Area. We need to continue to facilitate dialogue and provide guidance between research infrastructure funders, operators, and the scientific community.”

MARI SUNDLI TVEIT / CHIEF EXECUTIVE OF THE RESEARCH COUNCIL OF NORWAY (RCN)

scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/research-infrastructures

STRENGTHEN THE ROLE AND CONTRIBUTION OF SCIENCE IN TACKLING THE SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

THE SCIENCE EUROPE STRATEGY PLAN / 2021-2026

THE GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION

As the climate crisis and digitalisation dominate the societal agenda, many related challenges are yet to be adequately addressed at the European and global levels. Science Europe aims to gather researchers and policy makers to promote dialogue on science-informed decisions to support the so-called 'twin transition'. It does so by acting as a platform to foster co-ordination of actions at European level.

In 2022, Science Europe contributed to progressing the debate on green and digital transition issues. In November, the association published a report on [Interdisciplinary Research for the Green and Digital Transition](#), focused on activities that promote and support the mobilisation of all disciplines for tackling societal challenges. A follow-up publication and a dedicated event on how they support policy makers were both scheduled in March 2023.

In parallel, Science Europe organised several expert round-table discussions to further understand such complex societal challenges across the year. These discussions laid out priorities, trade-offs, and open challenges regarding the interrelations between the climate crisis and digitalisation. The challenge of 'greening' research activities, and ways to reduce the research carbon footprint were further explored.

The Working Group on the Green and Digital Transition continued his activities building on the [Call to Action to Research Organisations](#) launched in 2021.

The co-operation with [CESAER](#), the [International Sustainable Campus Network](#), and the [University of Strathclyde](#), grew into a permanent platform where information and joint actions were exchanged. At [ESOF2022](#), a joint session on 'Engaging researchers for the Net-Zero Transition' provided participants with concrete examples of climate actions and supported the preparation of a [COP27 lead-up event](#), joined by other partners. A report with the main event takeaways was published in April 2023. The mobilisation of science organisations for the Net-Zero Transition is expected to continue to grow in 2023.

Strengthening the voice of science in and for society also involves the important aspect of communicating with governments and policy makers. Science Europe therefore organised an event on [Good Advice for \(Young\) Science-Policy Advisors](#) in April 2022 to promote science-informed policy making. This event featured 16 engaging workshop takeaways, summarising key lessons learned from top experts on career perspectives for science-policy advisors, considering both individual skills, competencies, and training needed, as well as the possible professional paths and different organisations involved.

"With the world facing unprecedented challenges related to climate change, biodiversity loss, and digital transformation, science must play a central role in providing evidence-based solutions and informing policy decisions."

ÁNGELES GÓMEZ BORRERO / VICE PRESIDENT FOR INTERNATIONAL AFFAIRS OF THE SPANISH NATIONAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (CSIC)

Good Advice for (Young) Science-Policy Advisors: Lessons Learned:

[sciur.org/16-lessons-science-policy-advice](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

Science for Net-Zero Transition - COP27 lead-up event:

[sciur.org/op27-lead-up-videlst](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=...)

[scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/green-and-digital-transition](https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-priorities/green-and-digital-transition)

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Effective science communication can empower research and innovation systems to address global challenges and put public interests at the heart of how knowledge is produced, shared, and applied. Science Europe is committed to working with its Member Organisations to foster better and more effective science communication.

In the last few years, science communication has established itself as a discipline in its own right and the Working Group on Communication sharpened its focus on the topic of science communication, including trust in science, fake news, and disinformation.

Science Europe outlined a vision for science communication as an essential element of the research culture we want to build in a position statement entitled [Science Communication for Greater Research Impact](#).

“Given the challenging times we live in, Science Europe was compelled to start reflecting on how science communication plays an essential role in the research culture it wants to build.”

ANTONIO ZOCCOLI / PRESIDENT OF THE NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR NUCLEAR PHYSICS (INFN)

It aligned the Member Organisation in the initiation of actions that contribute to fostering more effective communication of science to society. These actions include creating pan-European opportunities to enhance trust in science, building partnerships to address misinformation and fake news, and developing institutional tools for researchers, such as training and guidance. The statement serves to guide future activities, including the organisation of a high-level conference in March 2024 to raise awareness amongst policy makers of the importance of science communication in research programmes.

The Working Group on Communication also supported communications activities that engaged the Member Organisations in developing and running campaigns on the three priority areas. An example was the #TalkingScience campaign that was launched during the High Level Workshop on Research Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Public Engagement (23 and 24 November). 33 Member Organisations shared their initiatives on this topic, which were promoted by Science Europe both on a dedicated webpage and on social media.

Science Europe calls on its members to:

- **Strengthen** the role that research institutions have in science communication
- **Create** pan-European opportunities to develop awareness, enhance relevance, and build trust in science.
- **Build** partnerships with science communication stakeholders and intergovernmental bodies
- **Develop** institutional tools for researchers to better communicate research.
- **Employ** new and diverse forms of knowledge communication

AFTERWORD

“We can proudly look back on the collaborative efforts between the Science Europe Office, the Governing Board, and our members in 2022. Together, we achieved significant milestones in shaping the European research landscape and providing crucial guidance on important policy areas.”

Notable accomplishments include the establishment of the Coalition for the Advancement of Research Assessment (CoARA), the publication of the Direction Paper on Open Science, and the Position Statement on Science Communication. These milestones have been made possible through the invaluable contributions of our Working Groups and the strategic directions set by the Governing Board.

As we embark on the journey through 2023, Science Europe remains committed to delivering added value to our members by sharing knowledge, fostering alignment, and promoting collaboration to enhance the efficiency of European research systems. Naturally, we continue to provide our best possible support to the National Research Foundation of Ukraine and to the Ukrainian researchers.

This year will also mark the mid-term review of our Strategy Plan, which covers the years 2021–2026. We value our members’ opinions and recommendations on the way forward and will contact them to provide their input.

In 2023, we will also be dedicated to strengthening Science Europe’s role in EU and global policy development, and developing compelling narratives that bridge the different areas of our strategic framework. Our focus will remain on shaping ERA policy developments, promoting investment in basic research, excellence, and academic freedom. We will contribute to enhancing brain circulation and provide input to the mid-term review of Horizon Europe. Brand new guidance on Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion is also foreseen.

Building on the shared values framework for the organisation of research, we will continue to support our members in embedding these values into institutional policies and further enhancing the quality of research. Our commitment to the initiative on reforming research assessment (CoARA) will also be carried forward. Ethics and integrity aspects related to research activities and science communication remain firmly in our spotlight, and we are actively attuned to the challenges and opportunities posed by Artificial Intelligence, which is also on our radar.

We continue fostering Open Science policies in Europe and at the global level, drawing from the direction paper. In addition, the Global Summit on Diamond Open Access in late 2023 will bring together the community of stakeholders engaged worldwide in strengthening the Diamond Open Access ecosystem. To further advance science–policy interactions and foster interdisciplinary collaboration for the green and digital transition we will engage in meaningful discussions with leaders from research organisations. Drawing on the position on science communication, together with our members we will underpin the collective capacity to communicate research more effectively.

My colleagues in the Office and I would like to thank our members wholeheartedly for their dedication to Science Europe and for their engagement in shaping and strengthening the European research system together. Through collective efforts and shared knowledge, we will continue to work towards a more prosperous and peaceful future for researchers and societies worldwide.

LIDIA BORRELL-DAMIÁN
SECRETARY GENERAL OF SCIENCE EUROPE

ANNEX

SCIENCE EUROPE'S GOVERNING BOARD MEMBERS IN 2022

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Schiltz, Marc <i>(President)</i>	Secretary General of the Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Gómez Borrego, Ángeles <i>(Vice-President representing RPOs) until July</i>	Vice-President for International Affairs of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Kalt, Angelika <i>(Vice-President representing RFOs)</i>	Director of the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Curaj, Adrian	Director General of the Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Damerval, Thierry	President/CEO of the French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Koenig, Matthias	Vice-President of the German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Levi, Marcel	President of the Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Sundli Tveit, Mari	Chief Executive of the Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Welham, Melanie	Executive Chair of the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Zoccoli, Antonio	President of the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy

HIGH-LEVEL POLICY NETWORK ON THE EUROPEAN RESEARCH AREA AND CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY	NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Abillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium	Marti, Simon	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Baanante, Ignacio	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain	Martinović Klarić, Irena	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Bak, Sebastiaan den	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands	Mico Egea, Victoria	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Bärenreuter, Christoph	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria	Mistrík, Robert	Slovak Research and Development Agency (APVV)	Slovakia
Barrionuevo, Marta	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain	Mortensen, Jakob Nedergaard	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Bell, Linda	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden	Muižniece, Lauma	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria	Nieto Garcia, Maria Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Boc, Mojca	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia	Noorma, Anu	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium	Ognis, Laure	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia	Pětrašová, Kamila	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany	Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Burg, Helena (Chair CBC)	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg	Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Butt, Dominique	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom	Poll, Myriam	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Curaj, Adrian	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania	Polotska, Olga	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Danielsen, Kristin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Sara-Kennedy, Rachael	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain	Słomińska, Kinga	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Domínguez, Elena	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain	Tamanis, Edmunds	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Dunon-Bluteau, Dominique	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France	Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Folea, Antoaneta	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania	Törnqvist, Stefan	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Groeneveld, Joël	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium	Torrent, Moira	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Hakala, Johanna	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland	Verbaeys, Isabelle	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Hamer, Kate	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom	Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway	Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Horst, Maja	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark	Wiley, Paul	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Kučera, Rudolf	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic	Woźniakowska, Justyna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands	Zagalo Pereira, Gonçalo	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Maguire, Teresa	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland	Zondaka, Elita	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Lidia Borrell-Damián (Chair ERA), **Adrien Braem** (ERA), **Mathilde Reumaux** (CBC), **Sara Cesari** (CBC) (April–July 2022)

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON MONITORING CROSS-BORDER COLLABORATION

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Absillis, Gregory	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Burg, Helena	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Butt, Dominique	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Dinkel, William	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Hiney, Maura	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Łazarowicz-Kowalik, Marta	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland
Martínez, Catalina	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Martin-Lanuz, Monica	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Plewinska, Honorata	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Raudvere, Kadri	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Repnik, Robert	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Strzebońska, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Tejada, Laura	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Učakar Petrovčič, Lucija	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Wojciechowska, Paulina	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Mathilde Reumaux

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON CHINA

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Bain, Magnus	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Bak, Sebastiaan den	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Bonenkamp, Berry	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Durrans, Sophie	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Grasso, Simona	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Hansteen, Thomas	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Krűßmann, Ingrid	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Schlepper, Gerrit Andreas	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wachter, Wolfgang	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wiley, Paul	United Kingdom Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Mathilde Reumaux

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON HORIZON EUROPE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancāns, Jānis	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Belocky, Reinhard	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Benner, Inga	UK Research Office (UKRI)	Belgium
Boljević, Jasminka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Bühler, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Devine, Ellenor	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Doménech, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Fängström, Britta	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Ferlaino, Francesco	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Kazai, Zsolt	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary
Kostka, Sylwia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Krogkær, Stine Bøg	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Kuipers, Joyce	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Lahtinen, Hannele (Co-Chair)	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Lindeløv, Anne	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Lindholm, Maria	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Martínez, Berta	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Møller, Tom-Espen	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Mortensen, Jakob Nedergaard	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Nakath, Richard	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Napa, Ülle	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Nash, Maria	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Pin, Pierre-Olivier	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Rodríguez, Cristina	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Serrano, Joaquín	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Szendrey, Adrienn	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Szepesvári, Krisztina (Co-Chair)	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary
Torrent, Moira	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Totland, Karin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Van Hauwaert, Ann	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Vistad, Rune	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Winger, Martin	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wittorski, Natacha	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Mathilde Reumaux

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON WIDENING ACTIVITIES

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Bühler, Sarah	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Kazai, Zsolt	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary
Kostka, Sylwia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Kotarba, Anna	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Munhá, Rui	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Napa, Ülle	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Pětrašová, Kamila	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Simion, Elena	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Szepesvári, Krisztina (Co-Chair)	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary
Totland, Karin	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Mathilde Reumaux

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON OPEN SCIENCE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Armesto, Lourdes	Spanish State Research Agency (AEI)	Spain
Barać Lauc, Lovorka	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Björke, Andreas	Swedish Research Council for Health, Working Life and Welfare (FORTE)	Sweden
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Bruce, Rachel	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Bruhn, Siri Lader	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Carić, Dejana	Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ)	Croatia
Chorošenin, Petr	Czech Science Foundation (GAČR)	Czech Republic
Cruz, Maria (Chair)	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Galica, Natalia	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Garnier, Martine	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Garrido, Julián	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Halling, Sanja	Swedish Research Council (VR)	Sweden
Hautala, Harri	Academy of Finland (AKA)	Finland
Irimia, Alina	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Jakobs, Tom	Luxembourg National Research Fund (FNR)	Luxembourg
Kirk, Ole	Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)	Denmark
Kita, Jean-Claude	Fund for Scientific Research (F.R.S.-FNRS)	Belgium
Kokorevičs, Arnis	Latvian Science Council (LZP)	Latvia
Kuznetsov, Andriy	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Meeus, Joke	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Mertens, Jan	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Mirlina, Liga	Latvian Council of Science (LZP)	Latvia
Montesanti, Annalisa	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Nordin, Lissa	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Novais, Joana	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ošo, Simon	Slovenian Research Agency (ARRS)	Slovenia
Pazik-Aybar, Aneta	National Science Centre (NCN)	Poland
Philipp, Tobias	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Podolieva, Alina	National Research Foundation of Ukraine (NRFU)	Ukraine
Ponsati, Agnes	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Primo, Elena	National Institute of Health Carlos III (ISCIII)	Spain
Qvenild, Marte	Research Council of Norway (RCN)	Norway
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Tamm, Priit	Estonian Research Council (ETAG)	Estonia
Winkler, Kathrin	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Wojtyra, Wiktor	Foundation for Polish Science (FNP)	Poland

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Bregt Saenen

MEMBERS OF THE TASK FORCE ON OPEN RESEARCH SOFTWARE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Ancion, Zoé	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Boccali, Tommaso	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Rieck, Katharina	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Katerbow, Matthias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Spanache, Ioana	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Martinez Ortiz, Carlos	Dutch Research Council (NWO)	Netherlands
Popa, Andrea	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding of Romania (UEFISCDI)	Romania
Perez, Daniel	Austrian Science Fund (FWF)	Austria
Karcher, Stefan	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany

SCIENCE EUROPE CO-ORDINATION:

Bregt Saenen

MEMBERS OF THE WORKING GROUP ON RESEARCH CULTURE

NAME	ORGANISATION	COUNTRY
Bergqvist Ampel, Linda	Swedish Research Council for Sustainable Development (FORMAS)	Sweden
Boehme, Olivier	Research Foundation Flanders (FWO)	Belgium
Bolliger, Isabel	Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)	Switzerland
Bondre-Beil, Priya	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Cañibano, Carolina (Co-Chair)	Spanish National Research Council (CSIC)	Spain
Chiarelli, Giorgio	National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN)	Italy
Cody, Anne	Health Research Board (HRB)	Ireland
Costa, Rosário	Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT)	Portugal
Downey, Frances (Co-Chair)	UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	United Kingdom
Fritch, Rochelle	Science Foundation Ireland (SFI)	Ireland
Gossink, Kasper	Dutch Research Council (now)	Netherlands
Grimm, Tobias	German Research Foundation (DFG)	Germany
Guyard, Laurence	French National Research Agency (ANR)	France
Györffi, Miklós	Eötvös Loránd Research Network (ELKH)	Hungary
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Adrien Braem	Senior Policy Officer Since October 2017
Sara Cesari	Policy Officer Since March 2022
Nicola Francesco Dotti	Senior Policy Officer Since October 2021
Stéphanie Flouquet	Personal and Administrative Assistant Since March 2021
Valentina Garoia	Communications Manager Since October 2021
Iwan Groeneveld	Communications and Events Officer Since June 2015

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Justine Moynat	Junior Communications Officer Since August 2022
Mathilde Reumaux	Senior Policy Officer Until March 2023
Artemis Rodopoulou	Office Manager Since August 2013
Bregt Saenen	Senior Policy Officer Since November 2021

SCIENCE EUROPE PUBLICATIONS 2022

TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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ERA AND HORIZON EUROPE

Towards Strengthened Research and Innovation Systems Across Europe: Science Europe Recommendations to Reduce Research and Innovation Disparities and Foster Brain Circulation	November
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Report of the 2022 High Level Workshop on ERA: Research Ethics and Integrity in the Context of Public Engagement	December
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EU DIGITAL AGENDA

Statement on the exemption of not-for-profit educational and scientific repositories, digital archives, and libraries from the Digital Services Act	April
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A Digital Legislation That Works for Science?	June
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GREEN AND DIGITAL TRANSITION AND INTERDISCIPLINARITY

Report of Symposium on Science for Net-Zero Transition: Linking Green Objectives with Societal Development	March
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Interdisciplinary Research for the Green and Digital Transition	November
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TITLE	PUBLICATION DATE
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OPEN ACCESS AND OPEN SCIENCE

Action Plan for Diamond Open Access	March
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Open Science As Part of a Well-Functioning Research System	October
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Briefing Paper on EOSC: Federating Research Infrastructures in Europe for air Access to Data	November
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RESEARCH CULTURE

A Values Framework for the Organisation of Research	June
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RESEARCH ASSESSMENT

Reaction to the Council Conclusions on Research Assessment and the Implementation of Open Science Policies	June
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Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment	July
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SCIENCE COMMUNICATION

Science Communication for Greater Research Impact	June
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Science Europe Annual Report 2021	June
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SCIENCE EUROPE'S MAIN EVENTS 2022

TITLE	DATE
Workshop on Diamond Open Access	2 February
Good Advice for (Young) Science–Policy Advisors	29 April
Diamond Open Access Conference	19-20 September
Science Europe Open Science Conference	18-19 October
Symposium Interdisciplinarity for the Net-Zero transition	3 November
Talent Retention: How can Europe tackle the challenges of Brain Drain and Capacity Building in EU-13 countries?	10 November
High Level Workshop on ERA: Research ethics and integrity in the context of public engagement	23-24 November
Global Research Council (GRC) European Meeting	12-13 December

Colophon

2022 SCIENCE EUROPE ANNUAL REPORT: RESEARCH AT THE HEART OF EUROPE'S AMBITION

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